

HISTORY OF COMPARATIVE LINGUISTICS AND ITS THE DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation: The article discusses the problem of terminological differentiation of two disciplines as part of comparative linguistics, studying related languages in diachronic (compare historical linguistics) and in synchrony; for terminological marking of the second In this direction, the term "comparative synchronic linguistics" is introduced.

Keywords: comparative method, comparative linguistics, terminology, comparative-historical, comparative synchronic, related languages, compares historical linguistics.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается проблема терминологического разграничения двух дисциплин в рамках сравнительного языкознания, изучения родственных языков в диахроническом (ср. Историческое языкознание) и синхронно; для терминологической разметки второго. В этом направлении вводится термин «сравнительное синхронное языкознание».

Ключевые слова: сравнительный метод, сравнительное языкознание, терминология, сравнительно-историческое, сравнительно-синхронное, родственные языки, сопоставление исторического языкознания.

The birth and functioning of the comparative-historical method became the basis for the formation of a new independent linguistic discipline- us - comparative historical linguistics, which is based on the work Fr. Bopp, R. Rusk, J. Grimm, A.H. Vostokov, written in the first quarter XIX century. [see: 1; 2. С. 6 and others]. Comparison method and comparative historical language knowledge contributed to the formation of other linguistic disciplines, languages based on comparison [see: 1-8; and etc.].¹

Thus, the development of comparative historical linguistics became the basis for the formation of linguistic disciplines such as linguistic typology, comparative typology, and comparative linguistics. All these linguistic disciplines are based on the use of a comparison method that, on the one hand, it unites them into one big whole - into a comparative language knowledge, and on the other hand, differentiate them into different linguistic disciplines [see: 1-3; nine; and etc.].

¹Рец. проф. Сапарова К.О. (УзГУМЯ, Ташкент); проф. У.М. Бахтикиреева (РУДН).

Comparative-historical linguistics explores the diachronic aspect related languages, identifying in them general concepts, categories, elements, proving the commonness, kinship of the common origin of the studied languages. For example, the study of the law of synchronism of the Turkic languages in diachronic from the general aspect shows that in all the Turkic languages two types of synchronicity: lingual synchronicity and labial synchronicity, which functioned simultaneously (in aggregate) and in the sound speech stream merged into one whole.

So, synharmonism, as the prosodic dominant of the Turkic sounding speech, historically consisted and consists of two components - the lingual singarmonism and labial harmony, which in the modern Turkic language knowledge, primarily in Kazakh, are terminologized in the following formulas- linguistic harmony, linguistic soft harmony; lingua- biosolid syngharmonicity, lingua-soft syngharmonicity [see: 10-13]. This is explained by the fact that labial harmony, in contrast to lingual syngharmonicity does not function independently: labial syngharmonicity does not exist outside of lingual singarmonism; labial harmony always functions together with lingual harmony, in words in which syngarmoling present hard or syngarmoling soft labial vowels.

The emergence of comparative historical linguistics in the XI-XUI centuries in Central Asia (M. Koshgariy, M. Zamakhshary, A. Navoiy, Z. M. Babur) and later in Western Europe and Russia in the XVII-XIX centuries (F. Bopp, R. Rask, J. Grimm, I. Dobrovsky, A.Kh. Vostokov). F. Bopp: typological classification of languages, root theory, agglutination theory. R.K. Rusk: establishing grammatical and phonetic correspondences, chronologization layers of vocabulary. J. Grimm: three stages of development of the human language, an appeal to sound changes, the law of the first movement of consonants in Germanic languages (the law Grima). A.Kh. Vostokov: "first-class" and "second-class" words, periodization of the Slavic language.

Comparative-historical linguistics in the middle of the nineteenth century. Development and application of the comparative-historical method in the study of language groups: F.Pott, T. Benfey, G. Curtius, A. Kuhn, A. Schleicher. A.F. Pott - Founder of Scientific etymology. G. Curtius: "The main features of Greek etymology." A.Kun - founder of linguistic paleontology and comparative mythology. A. Schleicher and his contribution to the development of the theory and practice of comparative historical research. Naturalistic concept. Comparative historical problems in the works of I.I. Sreznevsky.

Value works of F.I. Buslaev for the development of comparative historical linguistics. The concept of proto-language and the theory of the family tree. Types of similarities between languages. Criteria for determining linguistic relationship. Comparative Historical Issues linguistics in the works of young grammarians. The problem of changing the meanings of words in the interpretation of G. Paul. Psychological direction. Comparative historical problems in the works of F.F. Fortunatov. Questions and Answers comparative historical linguistics and the typology of languages in the works of Representatives Kazan linguistic school. Morris Swadesh (1909-1967) glottochronology method for measuring speed language changes (most often referring to lexicostatistics, i.e. comparing lists of 100 or 200 words of the compared languages from the most stable part of the vocabulary and taking the preservation rate of this list is equal to 81% and, accordingly, 86%, for one millennium) and determine on this basis the time of separation of related languages and the degree of closeness between them.

New criteria for internal reconstruction were developed, new theories of Indo-European vocalism and consonantism; further development - laryngeal theory. nine Restoration of accent-intonation types associated with certain grammatical paradigms (V.A. Dybo, V.M. Illich-Svitych). Reconstruction past states of a number of grammatical categories, the formation of new ideas about the oldest syntactic sentence structure. Successes in the study of Indo-European vocabulary (A. Walde, B. Pokorny.) Etymological dictionaries of ancient Indo-European languages - ancient Greek, ancient Indian, Latin, Baltic. Research on Indo-European onomastics and hydronyms (T. Milevsky, E. Benveniste, G. Schramm, M. Mayrhofer). Revisions of the idea of a single Indo-European source language (supporters of the idea continuity of the Indo-European language area, new linguists (M. Bartoli, V. Pisani, J. Bonfante, J. Devoto; N.S. Trubetskoy); authors of various and very controversial schemes dialectal division of the Indo-European region (J. Bonfante, I.A. Kerns and B. Schwartz, A.L.

Kroeber and K.D. Chretien, W. Porzig, H. Krae). Typological descriptions of Indo-European languages (P. Hartman). Further study of Indo-European antiquity (M. Gimbutas, P. Bosk-Gimper, R.U. Erich). Study of social, legal, economic institutions of the ancients Indo-Europeans (E. Benveniste). Interest in Indo-European mythology (J. Dumisiel, P. Thieme, G. Lommel, F.B. J. Kuyper).

Language changes: phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic. Explanation of the reasons for individual language changes. The importance of keeping track of language contacts for comparative historical linguistics. Contact influence in a

bilingual environment. Borrowing. Separation of original words from borrowings from close relative's languages. The value of borrowings for the study of language history. Etymology. The concept of etymology. Etymologization of primordial words. Etymologization stable phrases. Correlation of semantics and phonetics in etymology. Spatial (areal) linguistics and linguistic geography. The concept of genetic identity. Establishing the relationship of languages. Problems and principles of genealogical classification of languages. Major families of languages. Concept convergence. Methods of language divergence. Establishing correspondences between families and languages. The principles of proving the relationship of languages (phonetic and grammatical matches). Bopp's theory of agglutination.

Reconstruction of the phonological system and its phonetic interpretation. Reconstruction of grammatical units. External and internal reconstruction. The concept of linguistic time. Absolute and relative chronology. Dialectal division of the proto-language and issues of areal (spatial) linguistics. The level of models and interpretation in reconstruction. Reconstruction of morphology and syntax. The tasks of morphological reconstruction. Reconstruction of inflectional affixes. The problem of grammatical reconstruction values. Reconstruction of syntactic proto-linguistic morphemes. Reconstruction of additional distributions in the proto-language. Reconstruction of proto-linguistic word-formation. Reconstruction syntax. Lexical reconstruction. Examples of lexeme reconstructions. Reconstruction of lexemes, undergoing irregular transformations. Reconstruction of semantics based on restoration of the system of proto-linguistic oppositions. Computer comparative studies. Computer use in software research comparative historical linguistics.

Methodology for the comparative historical study of languages: comparative-historical method, glottochronology, reconstruction. Comparison as a universal linguistic method of cognition. Intralingual comparison. Types of interlingual comparison.

Methods for learning and describing languages. Linguistic Epistemology and Comparison Methodology. Scientific knowledge as a process. General scientific research methods and their application in linguistics. Introspection, observation, and experiment. Linguistic modeling. Comparative method. Comparative study of related and unrelated languages: implicit juxtaposition and language parallels. Typological method. Quantitative methods for defining typological language options. Types of contrastive analysis ("pure" and complex analysis, vertical and horizontal analysis, one-sided and two-sided analysis). "Error analysis": theory

and practice. Frequency dictionaries and their use in matching. Statistical methodology for learning language and text. Logical-mathematical modeling of language processes. Fuzzy logic. Descriptive methods: private techniques and techniques. Highlighting units. Distributive analysis. Distribution models. Component analysis. Methods for determining semantic factors. Determination of the semantic valence of linguistic units. Syntactic technique positions and distributive analysis. Methodology of transformation and transformational method. Opposite method. Nevertheless, we decided to use the term typology, since, in comparative typology, they are equally investigated as related, and unrelated languages. If we use the term (qiyosiy) typology (literally: comparative typology), then we "run into" the meaning in which the comparison of related languages is initially laid down, i.e. a comparative the typology of related languages, while the boundaries of the comparative typology logic are broader: it studies languages, regardless of their relationship.

The proposed concept of differentiation of linguistic disciplines is based on the use of a comparison method with terminological markings the scientific direction that studies the synchronous state of related languages in comparison, analogously: comparative synchronic linguistics. Quite it is possible that this is an inconclusive decision since science is one of the freest, democratic spheres of social activity of the individual and society (although the truth is always the same), therefore, it is acceptable (and, possibly, required) and other mono- and multi-innovation concepts.

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